

Single Particle Probabilities and Trial Runs in the Fermi-Dirac/Bose Einstein Cases

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If one tosses a die or coin, different outcomes occur with a probability $p(i)$ where i is the outcome. This probability may be measured by performing trial runs. For N trial runs, where N is very large, one might expect $Np(\text{outcome } i)$ results of an outcome i . In other words, $p(\text{outcome } i)$ is both the probability and describes the trial run. Even in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one has a probability $p(e_i)$ where e_i is kinetic energy (no $V(x)$) and reaction balance $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ represents trial runs. Thus the trial run is again characterized by $p(e_i)$ as e_i 's contribution.

It is, however, possible to have coupling of probabilities in certain physical situations even though $p(\text{outcome } i)$ still exists. In such a case, the number of outcome i results for N large trials is not $N p(\text{outcome } i)$. In other words, $p(i)$ does not fully describe the trial run. There may be other physical rules in place. If elastic scattering of particles is the way trial runs occur, $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ represents the salient information in the problem and even if there is nonindependence of $p(\text{outcome } i)$ in the scattering, one should at least obtain a function $Q(p(e_1))$ such that $Q(p(e_1)) = -e_1/T$. $Q(p(e_i))$, however, need not be $p(e_i)$.

We consider the physical rule given by Pauli stating that only one particle may fit in an energy level (no spin). Thus there is either 0 or 1 particle in the level. This should inhibit scattering, so the trial run is no longer simply described by $p(e_i)$. Rather the probability to scatter into level e_j is $(1 - n(e_j))$ and so one has: $n(e_1)[1 - n(e_3)] n(e_2)[1 - n(e_4)] = n(e_3)[1 - n(e_1)] n(e_4)[1 - n(e_2)]$ where $n(e_j)$ is the average occupancy, a number between 0 and 1. The opposite of only 0 or 1 particle in a state e_i , is to have any possible number of particles in this state and an enhancement, not a hindrance given by $1 + p(e_j)$. This is only a guess, but experiment shows that bosons follow this rule.

Given a definition of trial runs in terms of the inhibition and enhancement factors, one may do two things. First, since the trial rule seems to involve different numbers of particles in a state associated with a $p(e_i)$, one may consider sums of $p(e_i)$ (power number of particles) when describing the system statistically (i.e. grand canonical scheme). This approach gives rise to linear terms $(a + bp(e_i))$ which may in turn be formulated in terms of a factorial/arrangement equation which may be maximized subject to the constraints $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i n(e_i)$ and $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } n(e_i)$. We note that this maximization is not simply in terms of all degrees of freedom in the system, but is specifically linked with the rules associated with the trial runs and the constraints. We note, however, that issues seem to arise with the factorial scheme in the boson case.

Thus, overall we argue that a single particle probability and its trial run scheme are key to establishing the statistical behaviour of a system. (We also note that single particle independent probability, which is an approximation, also affects the final results.)

Single Particle Probabilities

Given a system of many identical particles, it seems one should be able to focus on $p(e_i)$ i.e. single particle probabilities based on e_i (kinetic energy) without any concern for other particles. This implies a kind of independence of the particles even though this is physically not the case,

For example, if the entire system has an energy of E and two single particles have $E/2$ and $E/2$ energy respectively, this imposes the constraint of 0 energy on all of the rest of the particles $N-2$, which may be a huge number. This, however, is a scenario with very little probability, it is assumed, so statistical mechanics seems to deal with an independent single particle scenario which leads to relaxation of a total sharp E (energy) [or even N (number of particles)] constraint. For example, writing:

$$\left\{ \sum_{i} p(e_i)^{N_{\text{on}i}} \right\}^N \quad ((1))$$

creates products of $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ etc with N factors, but possibly different total energy values. Thus treating particles as independent gives rise to an averaging over total E such that E_{ave} is E . This is called the canonical distribution approach in statistical mechanics.

A single particle has energy e_i at some time, but undergoes interactions and changes to e_j then later to e_k etc. Thus this has the appearance of trial runs such as tossing a coin or die. The difference, however, is that for a coin or die toss, there is no interaction of probabilities. The probability to obtain a 2 in the toss of a die is dependent on $p(2)$. It turns out that this is not the case in all two body scattering scenarios.

In the case of Fermi-Dirac scattering, a particle cannot scatter into an occupied state (if there are no spins for example). If one considers a scattering balance equation for an average system, there is a probability for a state e_j to be occupied given by $n(e_j)$, hence a probability $1-n(e_j)$ for it to be empty. On average there is a probability for $n(e_i)$ for a particle to be in state e_i . If one writes a probability balance equation for probabilities then:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_1)(1-n(e_3)) n(e_2)(1-n(e_4)) = n(e_3)(1-n(e_1)) n(e_4)(1-n(e_2)) \quad ((2b))$$

Thus $n(e_1)(1-n(e_3))$ and not $n(e_1)$ is the probability for an e_1 to possibly scatter into e_3 . Given that e , kinetic energy, in $((2a))$ is the salient information in the problem one expects $((2b))$ to be written in terms of:

$$F(n(e_1)) F(n(e_2)) = F(n(e_3)) F(n(e_4)) \quad ((3))$$

Thus $F(n(e_i))$'s behave as independent quantities in scattering, but are no longer probabilities. These ideas have been expressed in (1) and (2). There the approach is to use $F(p(e_1))$ as a new kind of probability and maximize arrangements subject to constraints.

$F(p(e_i))$, however, is not really a probability so in this note we wish to consider standard information theory arguments for $p(e_i)$ and see how they are modified.

Information Theory

Information theory often deals with independent probabilities (such as those of a die or coin). In such a case, a set of N trial runs may be made. If N is very large, one expects $Np(i)$ outcomes for event i . The product probability for N trial runs is:

Probability for any N trial runs = Product over i =1 to N $p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)}$ ((4))

$\ln(\text{Probability for any N trial runs}) = \sum \text{over } i \text{ } N p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ ((5))

For N very large, all N trial run sets have the same probability, but the events i are permuted. The probability is 1 over the number of permutations i.e.

$N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!$ ((6)) where $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$ ((6))

Thus ((5)) and the \ln of ((6)) are compatible.

This still does not give a value for $p(e_i)$. If one wishes to have as many permutations as possible, one may maximize $\sum \text{over } i \text{ } n(e_i) p(e_i)$ subject to the constraint $\sum \text{over } i \text{ } e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. Given that one considers single particle $n(e_i)$ without any constraints with other $n(e_j)$ s, one already considers a situation where all E_{total} values are allowed. The maximization process leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution: $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) C(T)$ where $C(T)$ is a normalization constant.

Non-Independent Probability Trial Runs

In the case of a die, one tosses it and there are 6 possible outcomes. With a particle, elastic scattering occurs. It is possible to have the scenario:

$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ ((7))

This leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann result. Elastic scattering, however, may not be so simple. Ultimately, given that e is the salient information in the problem one would like to have an equation: $g(n(e_1))g(n(e_2)) = g(n(e_3))g(n(e_4))$, but $g(n(e_i))$ need not be $n(e_i)$. This suggests that scattering probabilities may be coupled. For example, in the Fermi-Dirac case, in order to have e_1 scattering into e_3 on average, one has the product of a $n(e_1)(1-n(e_3))$ because e_3 has to be empty. Thus there is a coupling of probabilities. This coupling is due to a principle called Pauli's principle which states that two particles cannot occupy the same set of quantum numbers. Probability trial runs (elastic scattering) seem to be associated with probability coupling based on the average number of particles in a state. If the Pauli principle states that one may only have 0 or 1 particle, the other physical scenario is more than one particle. In other words, the Pauli principle inhibits scattering, while the opposite scenario (more than one particle) may enhance scattering. At this point this is simply a conjecture, but it suggests that if the number of particles in a state is a physical consideration, as in the Pauli principle case, one should, at least in principle, consider its complement. Thus one considers an enhancement of $(1+n(e_3))$ for scattering into state e_3 or:

$n(e_1)(1+n(e_3)) n(e_2)(1+n(e_4)) = n(e_3) (1+n(e_1)) n(e_4)(1+n(e_2))$ ((8a))

Solving ((8)) with $(e_1-u)+(e_2-u)=(e_3-u)+(e_4-u)$ yields the Bose-Einstein (BE) distribution:

$$n(e_i) = 1 / \{ \exp((e_i-u)/T) - 1 \} \quad ((8b))$$

Two parameters, T and u are needed to fix average energy and particle number.

The fact that one uses $n(e_i)$'s without considering energy restrictions means that all E_{total} are considered. Given that there may be many particles in a level e_i , one considers all N_{total} . In both cases, averages should be E_{ave} and N_{ave} .

As a result, one expects ((4)) to be modified. In (2), we argued that one may use a new kind of probability $g(n(e_i))$ in ((4)) which behaves in an MB manner, but with the constraints $\sum_i n(e_i)$ and $\sum_i n(e_i) e_i$. $g(n(e_i))$, however, is not really a probability. Here we wish to retain $n(e_i)$, but to note that outcome e_i should no longer appear $N_p(e_i)$. We thus ask: How often should an outcome i appear? Assume that $N_p(e_i)$ is replaced with $F(n(e_i))$. In the case of the BE (Bose-Einstein) distribution, one may write an entropy type expression as:

$$(1-n(e)) \ln(1-n(e)) - n(e) \ln(n(e)) \quad ((9)) \text{ and maximize it with respect to } n(e) \text{ and } n(e)$$

One may consider $p(e) = n(e)/N$ and $F(n(e))$ replacing $N_p(e)$ in ((4)). Then ((9)) suggests that one maximize: $F(n) \ln(n/N)$ subject to the constraints above. This suggests that::

$$F(n) \{ \ln(n/N) \} = (1-n(e)) \ln(1-n(e)) - n \ln(n) \quad \text{or} \quad F(n) = \{ (1-n) \ln(1-n) - n \ln(n) \} / \ln(n/N) \quad ((10))$$

Thus $n(e)$ still exists, but changes in trial runs are much more complicated, i.e. related to $F(n)$ in ((10)).

Grand Canonical and Factorial Schemes

It may be seen using reaction balance, which defines the trial runs, together with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ that:

$$n(e_i) = 1 / \{ \exp((e_i-u)/T) -/+ 1 \} \quad - \text{ for bosons, } + \text{ for fermions} \quad ((11))$$

Given that the change to trial runs involves occupancy i.e. particle numbers in e_i , one may consider the following forms:

$$\text{Fermi-Dirac: } p(e_i)^0 + p(e_i) = 1 + p(e_i) \quad (0,1 \text{ or one particle occupancy}) \quad ((12a))$$

$$\text{Bose-Einstein } \sum_{i=0}^{\text{infinite}} p(e_i)^i = 1 / (1-p(e_i)) \quad ((12b))$$

If $p(e_i) = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ i.e. the MB result, then ((12a)) and ((12b)) are part of partition functions i.e. single particle probability combinations (i.e. sum over n for each e_i) and products of these, yields $\ln Z = \sum \ln(1+p(e_i))$ (FD) or $\ln Z = -\sum \ln(1-p(e_i))$. These in turn may be differentiated

with respect to $\exp(u/T)$ to yield $n(e_i)$ values. Thus the grand canonical approach follows by examining the result of trial runs ((8)) and an equivalent result for the Fermi-Dirac case.

In other words one may consider: $Z = \text{Sum over } E, N \exp(-(E-uN))$ where $E = \text{Sum over } i e_i n(i)$ and $N = \text{sum over } i n(i)$.

Given the forms of ((12a)) and ((12b)), one may notice the link with factorials using Stirling's approximation for large N : $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N)$.

For fermions one has: $\ln(1! \{ n! (1-n)! \})$ maximized with respect to $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(i)$ and $\text{sum over } i n(i)$ because n is less than 1.

For bosons, one has: $\ln\{ (n+1)! / (n!) \}$ maximized with respect to the same constraints. In some cases (3), it is suggested one use: $\ln\{ (n(i) + g_i - 1)! / [n(i)! g_i!] \}$ where g_i is the degeneracy i.e. proportional to 4×3.14 ppdp, but no degeneracy factor is used in the reaction balance or grand canonical approaches to obtain the BE form. Furthermore the resulting answer is g_i multiplied by the BE distribution meaning one could have a $g_i=1$.

We suggest that there may be some issues present in the factorial approach. First:

$\ln[(n+1)!/n!] = \ln(n+1)$ so its derivative with respect to n is $1/(n+1)$ where it is assumed that $n \gg 1$ because one may make N as large a number as one wants. This restricts $(e_i-u)/T$ to being close to zero, but no such restriction exists in the BE distribution. In fact, in the classical region, $\exp((e-u)/T)$ is very large so $(e-u)/T$ cannot be small.

If one uses Stirling's approximation, $d/dn \ln[(n+1)!/n!] = \ln((n+1)/n)$, but $n \gg 1$ so this may be expanded in a series and again $(e-u)/T$ must be very small.

What if one uses g_i as in (3), but g_i is small compared with $n(i)$? In this case:

$$d/dn \{ \ln \text{ factorials} \} = \ln((n(i)+g_i) / n(i)) = \ln(1 + g_i/n(i))$$

If $g_i/n(i)$ is small, then one may again perform an expansion in small values $g_i/n(i)$ so it seems $(e-u)/T$ must be small again.

One approach to obtaining the BE result is to redefine the derivative:

$$d/dn f(n) = f(n+1) - f(n) \quad ((13))$$

We begin with: $\ln(n! / (n-1)!)$ instead so that:

$$d/dn \ln(n) = \ln(n+1) - \ln(n) = \ln[(n+1)/n] = -(e_i-u)/T$$

$$\text{Or } n = 1 / \{ \exp((e_i-u)/T) - 1 \} \quad ((14))$$

((14)) is arrived at with no use of Stirling's approximation and should hold in general with no small $(e_i - u)/T$ restriction although a discrete approach to differentiating n is used and $\ln(n!/(n-1)!)$ no longer has a simple physical interpretation it seems which begs the question: Does a factorial approach make sense in the BE case? Another possible way to obtain results is to use an unusual degeneracy g_i which is automatically of the order of n , but is not affected by the derivative d/dn .

Thus mathematically the trial run reaction balance results may be written in either grand canonical form or possibly in a factorial/arrangement form which may be maximized subject to constraints (although there are issues for the BE case). For the grand canonical form, $\exp(-\epsilon_i - u)$ used for $p(\epsilon_i)$ is already maximized.

Momentum Degeneracy

In the above section we noted that results from the reaction balance of scattering i.e. the trial run approach may be written as a maximization of the \ln of a factorial/permutation expression subject to two constraints (although with problems in the BE case). We note that, in the above, $n(\epsilon_i)$ is used in this result, but no mention of other degrees of freedom such as the direction in which a momentum vector (associated with ϵ_i) points. Thus, it seems one does not simply maximize all possible arrangements of all degrees of freedom in a problem. Rather, the degrees of freedom seem to be linked to the constraints of the maximization process and ultimately it is the trial run process which governs the physics behind the statistics. Thus we caution reading too much into the \ln factorial function which is called entropy in such cases.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that in the tosses of a coin or die, or even for Maxwell-Boltzmann distributions, one focuses on $p(i)$, the probability for a single outcome, because trial runs are governed strictly by this probability value. Thus trial runs are not a separate and different part of the problem. For more complicated problems, however, a trial run may be defined by a physical process which involves more than $p(i)$. For example, Pauli stated that only one particle may be in each ϵ_i level (no spin). For $n(\epsilon_i)$ to change into $n(\epsilon_j)$ there is an inhibition probability of $(1 - n(\epsilon_j))$ where $n(\epsilon_j)$ is the average number of particles in state ϵ_j . As a result, one does not simply have $n(\epsilon_i)$ in the problem, but $n(\epsilon_i)(1 - n(\epsilon_j))$. The form $n(\epsilon_1)n(\epsilon_2) = n(\epsilon_3)n(\epsilon_4)$ becomes $n(\epsilon_1)[1 - n(\epsilon_3)] n(\epsilon_2)[1 - n(\epsilon_4)] = n(\epsilon_3)[1 - n(\epsilon_1)] n(\epsilon_4)[1 - n(\epsilon_2)]$. Then $n(\epsilon_i) / [1 - n(\epsilon_i)]$ behaves as a new kind of average occupancy quantity for trial runs. $-\ln$ of this is linked to $(\epsilon_1 - u)/T$ i.e. by comparison with $(\epsilon_1 - u) + (\epsilon_2 - u) = (\epsilon_3 - u) + (\epsilon_4 - u)$. Two parameters $1/T$ and u/T are needed to fix E_{ave} and N_{ave} . In other words, simply because a $p(\epsilon_i)$ or $n(\epsilon_i)$ exists, does not mean trial runs are dependent exactly on this form.

The Pauli principle holds for fermions. The complement of it is to allow all numbers of particles in a level i.e. consider an enhancement factor of $(1 + n(\epsilon_i))$ if a particle scatters into ϵ_i . Experimentally this is verified for bosons.

We have shown that the formalism of reaction balance applied to the proper type of trial run yields $n(e_i)$ values, but these values may be obtained, mathematically, two other ways. First, one may consider MB probabilities in a grand canonical scheme: $\sum \exp(-(E-uN)/T)$ where $E = \sum e_i n(e_i)$ and $N = \sum n(e_i)$. In other words one has MB type probabilities for a given e_i (but with two parameters) $\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ and considers $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(e_i)^n$ for bosons (and a similar expression for fermions). This is linked with having different numbers of particles in each level and gives the same result as an enhancement factor.

Alternatively one may mathematically create a factorial/permutation expression which yields the same result as the grand canonical result or the trial run reaction balance. \ln of this expression may be maximized with respect to the constraints $\sum e_i n(i)$ and $\sum n(i)$ to yield the same result and \ln of the factorial expression is called entropy. Issues, however, seem to arise in the Bose-Einstein case as we have noted above.

We argue that the statistical problem is described by the concept of $p(e_i)$ ($n(e_i)$) and the form of the trial runs which are not necessarily also described by $n(e_i)$ as in the toss of a coin or die. Given that one uses single particle values $p(e_i)$ or $n(e_i)$ without constraints on energy, the reaction balance approach is already equivalent to a canonical one. In other words, trial runs may involve the coupling of different single particle average numbers $n(e_i)$.

References

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